

Luminous Flux and Illumination through the vertical regular n-gon

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We view the following situation in vacuum. A light source Q has a distance r from a vertical regular n-gon. The n-gon has the exterior circle radius R and the incircle radius δ (see fig.). The light source has the luminous intensity I .

$$\alpha = \frac{360^\circ}{2n} = \frac{180^\circ}{n}$$

$$\cos \alpha = \frac{\delta}{R} \quad r > 0$$

We search an integral form, because then it is possible to treat the n-gon with pure air.

$x \in [0, R]$ $l = \sqrt{r^2 + x^2}$ is the distance

The illumination E is:

$$E(x) = \frac{I}{l^2} = \frac{I}{r^2 + x^2}$$

The angle of inclination β can be described:

$$\cos \beta(x) = \frac{r}{l} = \frac{r}{\sqrt{r^2 + x^2}}$$

It will be integrated with x from 0 to δ and from δ to R in circles.
From δ to R we can use only a reduced perimeter that is in the n -gon. It can be seen that the reduced perimeter is:(see the last but one figure)

$$U_n(x) = 2\pi x \cdot \frac{[\frac{180^\circ}{n} - \arccos(\frac{\delta}{x})] \cdot 2n}{360^\circ}$$

in radian measure:

$$U_n(x) = 2\pi x \cdot \frac{[\frac{\pi}{n} - \arccos(\frac{\delta}{x})] \cdot 2n}{2\pi}$$

$$= 2nx \cdot \left[\frac{\pi}{n} - \arccos \left(\frac{\delta}{x} \right) \right]$$

For the luminous flux through the regular n-gon it can be recognized:

$$\Phi = \int_0^{\delta} 2\pi x \cdot E(x) \cdot \cos \beta(x) dx + \int_{\delta}^R U_n(x) \cdot E(x) \cdot \cos \beta(x) dx$$

$$\Phi = 2\pi I r \cdot \int_0^{\delta} \frac{x dx}{(r^2 + x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} + 2n I r \cdot \int_{\delta}^R \frac{\left[\frac{\pi}{n} - \arccos \left(\frac{\delta}{x} \right) \right] \cdot x dx}{(r^2 + x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

$$r > 0$$

Gram's determinant (see Forster [1] §3 and §14:)

The n-gon is in the origin.

$$\bar{x} \in [0, R]$$

$\vec{c}(\vec{p}) = \vec{x}$ is a possible parametrization for both integrals.

$$D\vec{c} = 1 \quad (D\vec{c})^T = 1$$

$$g_c = \det [(D\vec{c})^T \cdot D\vec{c}] = 1$$

Thus the Gram's determinant is 1. Thus (1) is a complete expression of the luminous flux.

Now we view the same situation in medium (for example pure air) with constant density and constant absorption coefficient m . Then the luminous flux through the regular n -gon can be written:

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi &= 2\pi I r \cdot \int_0^{\delta} e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{x dx}{(r^2+x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &+ 2n I r \cdot \int_{\delta}^R e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{[\frac{\pi}{n} - \arccos(\frac{\delta}{x})] \cdot x dx}{(r^2+x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &= 2\pi I r \int_0^R e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{x dx}{(r^2+x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \\ &- 2n I r \cdot \int_{\delta}^R e^{-m\sqrt{r^2+x^2}} \cdot \frac{\arccos(\frac{\delta}{x}) \cdot x dx}{(r^2+x^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$r > 0$$

The first integral is the same as at the vertical circle and can be calculated in the same way.

The second integral cannot be integrated exactly (as far as known). The possibilities are numerical integration and the Monte-Carlo-method.

We treat an example with $R = r = 1$ metre and the luminous intensity 1 Candela. We calculate for some numbers of edges n the luminous flux. The absorption coefficient m of pure air is at 435 nanometres wavelength $0.00003 \text{ metre}^{-1}$. The result is the following table, the luminous flux is given in Lumen:

n	luminous flux
3	0.9667
4	1.3594
5	1.5374
6	1.6321
7	1.6883
8	1.7245
9	1.7491
10	1.7666
11	1.7796
12	1.7893

References

- [1] Otto Forster "Analysis 3" 2.edition 1983 Vieweg Verlag Brunswick
- [2] Harald Schröder "Luminous Flux and Illumination" Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag Berlin 2001